

Application of Infographics: An Effective Visual Language in Digital Age Social Advertising

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Abstract: Language is extremely important in today's digital age. Visual language is of particular importance in the flow of changing technology and development. Infographics are the visual language used to convey ideas in almost every field in today's life. Infographics are the visual language needed to effectively communicate the technical knowledge, information, and ideas of today's digital world. Infographics are a useful visual language. Today's modern thought transmission has brought more dynamism and flexibility to print and electronic media than ever before. It takes time to understand any language. If the language is simple and easy, then it is understood quickly. But some information, and knowledge is in technical form. Such information is dull, cumbersome, and boring. In today's information age, with modern technology, the expectations of the public are constantly increasing and, in an effort, to meet them, professional social media companies are embracing digital transformation in a big way. In such a time, the use and application of infographics are being implemented day by day at various levels through various mediums. Digital media is an interactive media.

Practical Implications: The Covid-19 pandemic was a very important period for the entire world. During this period, there was a huge strain on the entire health system. This period was very important and challenging for India. Social awareness has been carried out effectively through effective social advertising campaigns by the Government of India. The objective of this research paper is to understand the effectiveness of the visual language of Infographics in the digital social advertising area particularly in the context of social health advertising campaigns of India.

Keywords: Covid-19 Pandemic; Digital Age Social Communication; Infographics; Indian Social Advertising; Visual Language.

1. Introduction: Theoretical Framework

The proposed study is based mainly on Indian Infographics which are related to social communication such as social health advertising areas. After the COVID-19 pandemic, there are various changes and developments have occurred in Indian social health advertising in terms of the use of Infographics as an effective communication tool. Social behavioral changes are constantly evolving with modern technology in terms of the mass use of social media among urban and rural populations. This scenario is embracing digital transformation in a big way. In such a time, the use and application of Infographics are being implemented day by day at various levels through various mediums. Infographics as a design element is used to convey complex or simple information/knowledge easily to target customers or mass groups through visual language. Language is extremely important in today's digital age. Visual language is of particular importance in the

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flow of changing technology and development. Infographics are the visual language as well as communication tools used to convey ideas in almost every field today. Infographics are the visual language needed to effectively communicate today's digital world's technical knowledge, information, and ideas. Today's modern thought communication is more dynamic and flexible than ever before in print and electronic media. The main reason for this is the unique development in the science and technology field. This has brought the whole world closer to communicating various ideas across geographical boundaries (Dick, 2020). Although Infographics are supposed to convey simple, easy ideas of information/knowledge, such ideas are effectively conveyed if they are expressed through the unique harmony of simple graphics images, and letters/alphabets. It remains in the long-term memory of the readers, and the target customer segment, and achieves the objective of thought transmission. Pictorial language is global (Geismar et al., 2011). It has no barrier of language, geographical region, or gender discrimination. Because of this, visual language is more effective than verbal language. In a linguistically and culturally diverse developing democratic country like India, Infographics are needed for effective mass communication given their spreading potential

2. Research Question

In today's digital age, what and how is the use of Infographics in social advertising changing the process of communication?

3. Infographics

Humans have used pictorial language to express their feelings and thoughts since prehistoric times. Pictorial language is the primitive language of man. Further, human beings have invented language by using the brain which is progressing according to the time provided by nature. Scripts have been created from this energetic force. Visual imagery has been very important in human life since prehistoric times (Siricharoen, 2013). It was during this period that man developed pictorial language according to his natural intellectual powers in his primitive stage. The impact of pictorial language and its ability to be remembered remains in the human consciousness for a long time. Thought transmission is effective if both the picture and word elements are similar to each other in thought transmission. In viable thought transmission, the elements of picture and word cannot be separated (Vizoso & Figueiras, 2020). Even in the future, the companionship of pictures and letters will continue to be more exciting and positive and to express definite human feelings, words have to be used as an alternative to language (Dwivedi et al., 2021). Through words, human emotions are expressed in a visible and invisible form. Visual expression in print media is of equal intensity. It has the same effect on the human mind-sense (Krum, 2013)

3.1. Infographics: An Effective Visual Language

Pictorial language has been close to humans since its origin. Because pictorial language is a primitive language. Although the forms of nature are tangible and abstract, the importance of pictorial language does not diminish (Naparín & Saad, 2017). Man's instinct for drawing has led him to verbal language and script. The creation process of language and script was accepted by man as a challenge. After years of conceptual and artistic brainstorming, humans have created a language and script that are easy to transmit thoughts. From prehistoric times to today's modern digital era, languages and scripts have undergone various rituals. Therefore, the language and script have become flexible and fluid. This characteristic is their permanence. These qualities of languages and scripts will be of special importance in the future. Language and script are human-centric (Krum, 2013). Language and script have played an important role in the entire social and cultural structure of human beings. The famous anthropologist Charles Darwin's theory of evolution applies to the change and development of language and script. Language and script change their form according to time and need (Geismar & Chermayeff, 2011). This is a natural process. Social, cultural, and economic changes are responsible for this. Visual language is a process of thought transmission. Broadcasting that uses visual elements is called visual broadcasting. Verbal communication is no different from the transmission of human thought. However, such verbal transmission of ideas has limitations. Dialects are globally limited to countries and social human groups. Visual language is a global language. Visual language does not have the barrier of spoken language. Perception in the visual component supports and facilitates the visual component through thought transmission. Therefore, visual language becomes very important in the thought transmission process. Visual language is used while presenting an idea, or concept in a dramatic form. We can visualize a verbal concept. Examples of applications of visual language are diagrams, maps, signs, symbols, and painting. Forming

this visual language includes the design elements of line, shape, color, form, motion, texture, pattern, direction, orientation, scale, angle, space, and proportion.

3.2. Digital Age

Today's modern thought transmission has brought more dynamism and flexibility to print and electronic media than ever before (Brody & Wozencroft, 2012). The main reason for this is the unprecedented development in science and technology. This has brought the whole world closer to transmitting ideas across geographical boundaries. It takes time to understand any language. If the language is simple and easy, it is easy to understand. But some information, and knowledge is in technical form. Such information is dull, cumbersome, and boring. With modern technology in terms of goods and services, consumer expectations are constantly evolving and business companies are adopting digital transformation on a large scale to complete. In such a time, the use and application of Infographics are being implemented day by day in various mediums at various levels. Digital media is an interactive medium.

4. Indian Social Advertising in the Digital Age

Social life is changing with changing times. With social development, some social problems and questions are created. The nature of problems and questions today is different than in the past. The nature of social problems and issues in developed countries and developing countries are different. Any social problem is complex. They are profound. They affect the growth rate. Such questions become complex in the overall process of human development. Efforts are being made to solve such problems and issues through government and social organizations. Health, social issues, literacy campaigns, financial education, voting, patriotism, and civics are some of the important issues facing India. Apart from this, some other social problems are facing India. Such as poverty, homelessness, weedy cigarette tobacco consumption, alcoholism, drug abuse, illiteracy, unemployment, gender discrimination, child sexual abuse, rape, sexual abuse, family violence, and dowry are some of the social problems that are deeply rooted.

India is a developed country. Health, social issues, literacy campaigns, financial education, voting, patriotism, and civics are some of the important issues facing India. All these questions and problems are complex. The government always tries to get to the root of these problems. The government works to solve these social problems and issues through various welfare schemes. In this regard, the government is using advertisements to create mass awareness and public education. Along with the government, various social organizations and private organizations are working to provide social awareness and public education with a sense of social responsibility. In the digital era, new concepts, ideas, and knowledge are created every day. Many of these concepts are interoperable. Infographics come in handy to explain it. Moreover, electronic devices like mobile phones, computers, and laptops are widely used by society. Then, due to the software that supports these electronic devices, various social media are being used by society. Such social media has become a major factor in thought transmission in today's time.

4.1. Impact of Infographics as an Effective Visual Language

The following examples indicate the importance of Infographics as an effective Visual Language in Social Advertising. Visual language is more effective than only text/script communication. Group thought is transmitted through various channels in society. This will be clear from the example given below. A signboard has been placed on the gate of a bungalow in Pune city (**Figure 1**). The following is the message on this. "Please do not stray your dog here if found the owner will also be strayed". This is a message regarding the dirt caused by pet dogs in front of the house or on the road. Pet owners can walk their dogs anywhere in public. This makes the area unhygienic due to this filth and there is a risk of smell and exposure while walking in the area. It is filthy to be like this. To avoid this, the house/bungalow owner has placed a warning board on his gate. This board uses very effective persuasive Infographics. In this way, Infographics can be effectively used to broadcast social messages.

Figure 1. Use of Infographics by an Indian Citizen for Social Communication
(Source: Social Media, Facebook / WhatsApp)

During the global COVID-19 pandemic, Infographics have played a very important role in conveying visual ideas for public awareness and public education about the coronavirus. Infographics are becoming useful in making message/idea transmission effective and easy through print and electronic advertisements disseminated by government and private organizations (Chandra, 2023; Joshi & Gupta, 2021). During the global COVID-19 pandemic, along with public awareness about the coronavirus, social media is being broadcasted by the government today on various other social issues and problems. For example, World Immunization Week, Seasonal Flu, Pradhan Mantri Safe Motherhood Mission, Beat the Hit, and World Malaria Day. (Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 5)

Figure 2. COVID-19 Social Health Awareness Advertisements by the Government of India
(Source: www.mp.gov.in)

Figure 3. Covid- 19 Social Health Awareness Advertisements by the Government of India (Source: www.mygov.in)

Figure 4. World Malaria Day; Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan Social Health Awareness Advertisements by the Government of India (Image Source: www.mygov.in)

Figure 5. Covid- 19 Social Health Awareness Advertisements by Government of India (Source: www.mygov.in)

5. Literature Review

Tufte, E. R. (2008) showed that Information Visualization is important in thought communication processes. In his published book ‘Envisioning Information’ states that maps, diagrams, interfaces, graphics, tables, and charts are useful for effective communication of ideas. These elements are especially useful for presenting complex information and knowledge in a simple and accessible manner. Information Visualization is the representation of the various elements required in the modern thought communication process in the process of transmitting complex information and knowledge.

There are two factors to consider when considering typefaces. One is the size of the typeface and the other is its expressiveness. Because these two elements work in the process of thought communication. If the typeface has the right aesthetic shape, its ability to convey an effective thought will increase and the purpose of conveying the thought is successful. The thought process expands and attracts a larger audience to people's target thoughts. A typeface works in a limited way in the writing process. In today's advanced technological era, the graphic aspects of the alphabet have become stronger. But in this changing digital age, the communication between typography and language seems to be getting lost. In today's typography, while creating typefaces, legibility and neatness are carefully considered. Typography preserves the creation and existence of language. Typography is important in today's information age as it helps to understand the complexities of language and the meaning of ideas contained in it. (Dwivedi et al., 2021; Poon, 2021)

Lankow, J., J. Ritchie, and R. Crooks. (2012) explained the present authors reflect deeply on the nature and scope of Infographics. The value, purpose, and scope of Infographics are determined by targeting target customer segments and audience groups to enable effective thought communication. Infographics are an important design element for business and marketing work. Infographics are a ubiquitous element in the publishing business.

Infographics are designed in this medium to convey ideas effectively and easily. Infographics are designed for the general reader, the target customer segment, considering their mental and intellectual abilities. Newspapers, magazines, and websites are successful media outlets through effective layouts, the combination of rich illustrations, and useful information.

Gobert, I., and J. van Looveren (2015) have worked on Visual Communication projects on different topics. By editing these projects, he has expanded the classification and grouping of various fields in the design field. In doing so, interviews were conducted with sixteen prominent information designers in the field, covering various methods and areas of Visual Communication projects. The two authors discuss and reflect on information design education by creating groups of students at the LUCA School of Arts in Brussels, Belgium, and conducting Visual Communication projects on various topics.

Murray Dick (2020), has extensively researched the topic of Infographics. In charting the history of Infographics, author Murray traces the evolution of the Infographic form step by step. Infographics have emerged as a visual design element as part of a cultural revolution concerning this topic. Infographics have become an extremely beneficial element in making news more interesting and informative, especially in the field of journalism. From the print culture that emerged in the 18th century to today's digital data journalism, Infographics as a design element has proven popular and useful in conveying ideas. Author Murray points out in his writing that Infographics and Data Visualization have become ubiquitous in today's daily media diet. Infographics are being used effectively in print newspapers, television news, and online social media.

6. Research Methodology

A qualitative research method is applied to this research topic. A descriptive analysis of Indian social advertisements has been conducted. For this research paper researcher used the secondary data system below. Secondary data was obtained from various digital social media sites- Facebook, WhatsApp, Internet.

7. Findings and Discussion

In the present research paper, a total of 50 different social advertisements have been studied using Infographics as a design element. These social advertisements have been published through the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare Department, Government of India. These advertisements have been published in print and electronic media from the year 2020 to the year 2023. Social advertising in India has changed a lot since the Covid-19 pandemic. Infographics are a design element that has been incorporated into health advertising in a specific manner. Infographics are a design element that combines visual images and words to effectively communicate ideas and knowledge. All types of information, knowledge, and technical information are easily conveyed to the readers through Infographics. This has led to an increase in the use of Infographics as a component of health advertisements published by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. Because of this, Infographics as a design element plays an important role in the social communication process

7.1. Use of infographics as a design element in Indian social health promotional advertisements. Year 2020 – 2023

- Measures related to illness

- Care to be taken regarding illness
- Medication to be taken during illness
- Measures to be taken to control seasonal diseases
- Pulse Polio Campaign Awareness
- Information about health services is available at various government health primary health centers, and district hospitals.

As shown in **Figure 6**, in India, health advertisements published by the Department of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India are being circulated in urban and rural areas. In this, 25 percent of advertisements in outdoor media are reaching the urban and rural population. In this- print media such as posters, pamphlets, hoardings, banners, newspapers, magazines, information booklets, etc.

As shown in **Figure 6**, in India, health advertisements published by the Department of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India are being circulated in urban and rural areas. In this, 75 percent of advertisements in electronic media are reaching the urban and rural population. It includes- electronic media such as TV, Internet, social media Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Google search, etc.

Figure 6. Infographics: Circulation of Social Health Advertisements in Rural & Urban India 2020- 2023

Figure 7. Characteristics of Indian Social Health Infographics

In this research paper, an attempt has been made to critically study the importance, function, and impact of Infographics in the context of an effective visual language in social advertising. An attempt has been made to study in depth the functions of Infographics as a design element, the importance of this element in the communication process, and the impact on the reader, the target audience. Infographics act as a design element and an effective visual language. Infographics as a design element have been used very content and effectively to convey social thought communication as shown in **Figure 1**. A citizen displayed an informative banner on his bungalow wall using a simple and meaningful Infographic design element with the message 'Please do not let your dog's loose here, if found, the owner will also be lost' to keep his bungalow area clean and hygienic. In this way, Infographics as a design element is precisely used to address a social issue or problem. This banner is widely circulated through digital social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Google Search, and the Internet.

Infographics as a design element have been used precisely in the health advertisements that are being circulated across the country through print and electronic media by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. The health advertisements show various factors in **Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4, and Figure 5**, various diseases, and their remedies, care to be taken by patients, drug treatment to be taken, government health activities, various public health centers, dispensaries, district, and state dispensaries, etc. Social awareness and health education are being done by accurately using Infographics as a design element through various advertising media. It seems to have a big positive impact on the mass population. **Figure 7** attempts to show that Infographics as a design element is an effective Visual Language. Social issues and problems are fundamentally complex, profound, and negative.

8. Conclusion

Easy and simple Infographics as a design element play an important role in conveying thoughts about such social questions and issues. Digital media is dynamic and flexible. Whereas print media is effective and easy to use. Infographics as a design element are characterized by aesthetic appeal, visual expression, simplicity, and content quality that effectively communicates ideas. In today's digital era, Infographics are very effective visual language in social communication tools in a developing democratic country like India, which is linguistically and culturally diverse. Infographics are planned to keep in mind the mindset of the target audience, their living conditions, and their educational level in a language they understand. They have a great influence on the public mind and society.

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